

GROWTH OF INDIAN STOCK EXCHANGES AND CREDIT RATING AGENCIES IN INDIA

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ABSTRACT

This paper examines the growth pattern of Indian capital market particularly Indian stock exchanges and credit rating agencies in India. The remarkable growth after 1985 can be clearly seen from the Table, and this was due to the favouring government policies towards security market industry. Trading in Indian stock exchanges is limited to listed securities of public limited companies. Here I have discussed aspect related to growth pattern of Indian stock exchanges and credit rating agencies in Indian little bit other factors. The Indian stock exchanges have undergone rapid growth during post financial sectors reform in on particular line. but it is found that after 2004-05 that new types of specific stock exchanges has been started in Indian capital market like stock exchanges in derivative market and in currency derivative market. Particular line trend of stock exchanges has declined and it was numbered 19 stock exchanges with increase by 7 other stock exchanges in specific area derivatives and currency derivatives, total 26 stock exchanges and 6 credit rating agencies recorded during 2012-13. Because of centralisation of trading deal on BSE, NSE and KSE have increased and trading on other stock exchanges has closed and declined. So the recognition granted to some stock exchanges Stands withdrawn and some stock exchanges has de-recognised under section 4(4) of SCRA. Due to pending litigation before the high court, some stock exchanges have not filed application for renewal of recognition which expired on the ground of lapse of time.

Keywords: - Growth, Indian, Stock Exchanges, Credit rating, Agencies.

INTRODUCTION

Many change happened during depression. Lahore Exchange was closed during partition of the country and later migrated to Delhi and merged with Delhi Stock Exchange. Bangalore Stock Exchange Limited was registered in 1957 and recognized in 1963. Most of the other exchanges languished till 1957 when they applied to the Central Government for recognition under the Securities Contracts (Regulation) Act, 1956. Only Bombay, Calcutta, Madras, Ahmedabad, Delhi, Hyderabad and Indore, the well-established exchanges, were recognized under the Act. Thus, during early sixties there were eight recognized stock exchanges in India (mentioned above). Here I have discussed aspect related to growth pattern of Indian stock exchanges and credit rating agencies in Indian little bit other factors. The Indian stock exchanges have undergone rapid growth during post financial sectors reform in on particular line. but it is found that after 2004-05 that new types of special stock exchanges has been started in Indian capital market like stock exchanges in derivative market and in currency derivative market. Particular line trend of stock exchanges has declined and it was numbered 19 stock exchanges with 7 other stock exchanges in specific area. Because of centralisation of trading deal on BSE, NSE and KSE have increased and trading on other stock exchanges has closed and declined. So the recognition granted to some stock exchanges Stands withdrawn and some stock exchanges has de-recognised under section 4(4) of

SCRA. Due to pending litigation before the high court, some stock exchanges have not filed application for renewal of recognition which expired on the ground of lapse of time.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

In the literature we are discussing history of Indian stock market. Indian Stock Markets are one of the oldest in Asia. Its history dates back to nearly 200 years ago. The East India Company was the famous institution in those days and business in its loan securities used to be transacted towards the close of the eighteenth century. By 1830's business on corporate stocks and shares in Bank and Cotton presses took place in Bombay. Though the trading list was broader in 1839, there were only half a dozen brokers recognized by banks and merchants during 1840 and 1850. The Uttar Pradesh Stock Exchange Limited (1940), Nagpur Stock Exchange Limited (1940) and Hyderabad Stock Exchange Limited (1944) were incorporated. The 1850's witnessed a rapid development of commercial enterprise and brokerage business attracted many men into the field and by 1860 the number of brokers increased into 60. In 1860-61 the American Civil War broke out and cotton supply from United States of Europe was stopped; thus, the 'Share Mania' in India begun. The number of brokers increased to about 200 to 250. However, at the end of the American Civil War, in 1865, a disastrous slump began. At the end of the American Civil War, the brokers who thrived out of Civil War in 1874, found a place in a street (now appropriately called as Dalal Street) where they would conveniently assemble and transact business. Ahmedabad gained importance next to Bombay with respect to cotton textile industry. After 1880, many mills originated from Ahmedabad and rapidly forged ahead. As new mills were floated, the need for a Stock Exchange at Ahmedabad was realised and in 1894 the brokers formed "The Ahmedabad Share and Stock Brokers' Association". In 1887, they formally established in Bombay, the "Native Share and Stock Brokers' Association" (which is alternatively known as "The Stock Exchange "). In 1895, the Stock Exchange acquired a premise in the same street and it was inaugurated in 1899. Ahmedabad gained importance next to Bombay with respect to cotton textile industry. After 1880, many mills originated from Ahmedabad and rapidly forged ahead. As new mills were floated, the need for a Stock Exchange at Ahmedabad was realised and in 1894 the brokers formed "The Ahmedabad Share and Stock Brokers' Association". What the cotton textile industry was to Bombay and Ahmedabad, the jute industry was to Calcutta. Also tea and coal industries were the other major industrial groups in Calcutta. After the Share Mania in 1861-65, in the 1870's there was a sharp boom in jute shares, which was followed by a boom in tea shares in the 1880's and 1890's; and a coal boom between 1904 and 1908. In the beginning of the twentieth century, the industrial revolution was on the way in India with the Swedish Movement; and with the inauguration of the Tata Iron and Steel Company Limited in 1907, an important stage in industrial advancement under Indian enterprise was reached. Indian cotton and jute textiles, steel, sugar, paper and flour mills and all companies generally enjoyed phenomenal prosperity, due to the First World War. In 1920, the then demure city of Madras had the maiden thrill of a stock exchange functioning in its midst, under the name and style of "The Madras Stock Exchange" with 100 members. In 1935, the stock market activity improved, especially in South India where there was a rapid increase in the number of textile mills and many plantation companies were floated. In 1937, a stock exchange was once again organized in Madras - Madras Stock Exchange Association (Pvt) Limited. In 1957 the name was changed to Madras Stock Exchange Limited. Lahore Stock Exchange was formed in 1934 and it had a brief life. It was merged with the Punjab Stock Exchange Limited, which was incorporated in 1936. The Second World War broke out in 1939. It gave a sharp boom which was followed by a slump. On account of the restrictive controls on cotton, bullion, seeds and

other commodities, those dealing in them found in the stock market as the only outlet for their activities. They were anxious to join the trade and their number was swelled by numerous others. Many new associations were constituted for the purpose and Stock Exchanges in all parts of the country were floated. The Uttar Pradesh Stock Exchange Limited (1940), Nagpur Stock Exchange Limited (1940) and Hyderabad Stock Exchange Limited (1944) were incorporated. In Delhi two stock exchanges - Delhi Stock and Share Brokers' Association Limited and the Delhi Stocks and Shares Exchange Limited - were floated and later in June 1947, amalgamated into the Delhi Stock Exchange Association Limited.

After Independence Period

Many change happened during depression. Lahore Exchange was closed during partition of the country and later migrated to Delhi and merged with Delhi Stock Exchange. Bangalore Stock Exchange Limited was registered in 1957 and recognized in 1963. Most of the other exchanges languished till 1957 when they applied to the Central Government for recognition under the Securities Contracts (Regulation) Act, 1956. Only Bombay, Calcutta, Madras, Ahmedabad, Delhi, Hyderabad and Indore, the well-established exchanges, were recognized under the Act. Thus, during early sixties there were eight recognized stock exchanges in India (mentioned above). The number virtually remained unchanged, for nearly two decades. During eighties, however, many stock exchanges were established: Cochin Stock Exchange (1980), Uttar Pradesh Stock Exchange Association Limited (at Kanpur, 1982), and Pune Stock Exchange Limited (1982), Ludhiana Stock Exchange Association Limited (1983), Gauhati Stock Exchange Limited (1984), Kanara Stock Exchange Limited (at Mangalore, 1985), Magadh Stock Exchange Association (at Patna, 1986), Jaipur Stock Exchange Limited (1989), Bhubaneswar Stock Exchange Association Limited (1989), Saurashtra Kutch Stock Exchange Limited (at Rajkot, 1989), Vadodara Stock Exchange Limited (at Baroda, 1990) and recently established exchanges - Coimbatore and Meerut. **Thus, at present**, there are totally twenty six recognized stock exchanges in India excluding the Over the Counter Exchange of India Limited (OTCEI) and the National Stock Exchange of India Limited (NSEIL). The Table given below displays the overall growth pattern of Indian stock markets since independence. It is quite evident from the Table that Indian stock markets have not only grown just in number of exchanges, but also in number of listed companies and in capital of listed companies. The remarkable growth after 1985 can be clearly seen from the Table, and this was due to the favouring government policies towards security market industry.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The primary purpose of this study is to obtain insight into the problem by the stock market trends. This study is undertaken with the following objectives:

1. To study the status of growth pattern of indian stock exchanges in the Indian capital market.
2. To investigate the numbers of credit rating agencies working in indian capital market.

NEED AND SCOPE OF THE STUDY

From the above mentioned review of various sources of studies, it has been observed that no specific study has been conducted in resent past to analyse the growth pattern of Indian stock exchanges and credit rating agencies. In this paper I have discussed different SEBI initiative relating to regulating the Indian stock exchanges during the period of this study.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY AND DATA AND SELECTED SAMPLE

The available data from the annual reports for the period from 1946 to 2013 of Sebi annual handbooks was tabulated against different order and initiative taken by SEBI. The Sebi initiative and sources were analysed to find out the current pattern of Indian stock exchanges and credit rating agencies in India. The data was further analysed to find out the changing trends over a period in Indian capital market.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

The analysis and interpretation has been discussed below:

Surprising Indian stock exchanges has registered a remarkable declining as apparent from the tables 1.1 & 1.2 below. During 1946-1980 growth pattern of Indian stock exchanges was poor. At that period only three stock exchanges were established. During the period 1980 to 1995 growths of Indian stock exchanges has registered remarkable upward trend in establishment of stock exchanges, number of stock exchanges has gone up from 9 to 22. In this period the growth pattern of Indian stock market was going high, as well as other factors considered like number of listed companies, number of stock issues of listed companies, capital of listed companies, market value of capital of listed companies, capitalisation per listed companies and market value of companies per listed companies.

Table: 1.1

THE GROWTH PATTERN OF THE INDIAN STOCK MARKET UPTO 1995									
Sl.No	YEARS	1946	1961	1971	1975	1980	1985	1991	1995
	PARTICULARS								
1	No. of Stock Exch.	7	7	8	8	9	14	20	22
2	No. of Listed Cos.	1125	1203	1599	1552	2265	4344	6229	8593
3	No. of Stock Issue of Listed Cos.	1506	2111	2838	3230	3697	6174	8967	11784
4	Capital of Listed Cos. (Cr. Rs.)	270	753	1812	2614	3973	9723	32041	59583
5	Market value of Capital of Listed Cos. (Cr. Rs.)	971	1292	2675	3273	6750	25302	110279	478121
6	Cap. per Listed Co. (4/2)(Lakh Rs.)	24	63	113	168	175	224	514	693
7	Mkt Value of Cap. per Listed Cos. (Lakh Rs.) (5/2)	86	107	167	211	298	582	1770	5564
8	Appreciated value of Cap. per Listed Cos. (Lak Rs.)	358	170	148	126	170	260	344	803

Source: Various issues of the Stock Exchange Official Directory, Vol.2 (9) (iii), Bombay Stock Exchange, Bombay.

As apparent from the table 1.2 below, during 2004 to 2006 stock exchanges were engaged in upward trend in growth of Indian stock exchanges. The number declined to 22 in 2006-2007 and during 2012-2013 only 19 stock exchanges were engaged in the Indian capital market in particular line as well as specific area concerned now stock exchanges in derivatives market has grown up to numbered 3 and stock exchanges in currency derivative has gone up to 4 from 2008 to 2012-2013. Quantity of shares traded in lakhs from 2004-05 to 2012-13 has increased from 1270535 to 2228176 respectively. Value of shares delivered in crore has increased from 2004-05 to 2012-13, 417502 to 968149 respectively.

Table 1.2

THE GROWTH PATTERN OF THE INDIAN STOCK MARKET FROM 2004-05 TO 2012-13									
Years									
Particulars	2004-05	2005-06	2006-07	2007-08	2008-09	2009-10	2010-11	2011-12	2012-13
Stock Exchanges (Cash Market)	23	23	22	19	19	19	19	19	20 (19*)
Stock Exchanges (Derivatives Market)	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	3
Stock Exchanges (Currency Derivatives)	-----	-----	-----	-----	3	4	4	4	4
Quantity of Shares Traded (Lakh)	12,70,535	14,85,947	14,11,945	24,67,606	21,58,786	33,42,947	28,02,464	22,61,023	22,28,176
Value of Shares Delivered (` crore)	4,17,502	6,81,025	8,41,343	14,47,220	8,41,202	12,28,612	12,81,441	9,69,086	9,68,149

- Notes:**
1. Hyderabad Stock Exchange, Coimbatore Stock Exchange and Saurashtra Kutch Stock Exchange have been granted exit by SEBI vide order dated January 25, 2013, April 4, 2013 and April 5, 2013 respectively.
 2. SEBI vide order dated September 3, 2007 refused to renew the recognition granted to Magadha Stock Exchange
 3. As per Securities Appellate Tribunal order dated October 4, 2006, the Mangalore Stock Exchange is a de-recognized Stock Exchange under Section 4 (4) of SCRA.

4. The Cochin Stock Exchange and Guwahati Stock Exchange have made applications for exit under SEBI circular dated May 30, 2012.
5. MCX-SX was granted registration in Cash and Equity Derivative Segment on July 10, 2012
6. The number of brokers and sub brokers in cash segment pertains to the number of Stock Exchanges existing in the respective year.
7. Qualified Depository Participants (QDPs) are SEBI registered Depository Participants (DPs) offering services to Qualified Foreign Investor (QFI)

Source: SEBI.

* At presents (on Apr 13-Dec 13) 19 stock exchanges.

Over The Counter Exchange of India (OTCEI)

The traditional trading mechanism prevailed in the Indian stock markets gave way to many functional inefficiencies, such as, absence of liquidity, lack of transparency, unduly long settlement periods and benami transactions, which affected the small investors to a great extent. To provide improved services to investors, the country's first ringless, scripless, electronic stock exchange - OTCEI - was created in 1992 by country's premier financial institutions - Unit Trust of India, Industrial Credit and Investment Corporation of India, Industrial Development Bank of India, SBI Capital Markets, Industrial Finance Corporation of India, General Insurance Corporation and its subsidiaries and CanBank Financial Services. Trading at OTCEI is done over the centres spread across the country. Securities traded on the OTCEI are classified into: Listed Securities - The shares and debentures of the companies listed on the OTC can be bought or sold at any OTC counter all over the country and they should not be listed anywhere else, Permitted Securities - Certain shares and debentures listed on other exchanges and units of mutual funds are allowed to be traded, Initiated debentures - Any equity holding at least one lakh debentures of a particular scrip can offer them for trading on the OTC. OTC has a unique feature of trading compared to other traditional exchanges. That is, certificates of listed securities and initiated debentures are not traded at OTC. The original certificate will be safely with the custodian. But, a counter receipt is generated out at the counter which substitutes the share certificate and is used for all transactions. In the case of permitted securities, the system is similar to a traditional stock exchange. The difference is that the delivery and payment procedure will be completed within 14 days. Compared to the traditional Exchanges, OTC Exchange network has the following advantages: OTCEI has widely dispersed trading mechanism across the country which provides greater liquidity and lesser risk of intermediary charges. Greater transparency and accuracy of prices is obtained due to the screen-based scrip less trading. Since the exact price of the transaction is shown on the computer screen, the investor gets to know the exact price at which s/he is trading. Faster settlement and transfer process compared to other exchanges. In the case of an OTC issue (new issue), the allotment procedure is completed in a month and trading commences after a month of the issue closure, whereas it takes a longer period for the same with respect to other exchanges. Thus, with the superior trading mechanism coupled with information transparency investors are gradually becoming aware of the manifold advantages of the OTCEI.

National Stock Exchange (NSE)

With the liberalization of the Indian economy, it was found inevitable to lift the Indian stock market trading system on par with the international standards. On the basis of the recommendations of high powered Pherwani

Committee, the National Stock Exchange was incorporated in 1992 by Industrial Development Bank of India, Industrial Credit and Investment Corporation of India, Industrial Finance Corporation of India, all Insurance Corporations, selected commercial banks and others. Trading at NSE can be classified under two broad categories:

- Wholesale debt market and
- Capital market.

Wholesale debt market operations are similar to money market operations - institutions and corporate bodies enter into high value transactions in financial instruments such as government securities, treasury bills, public sector unit bonds, commercial paper, certificate of deposit, etc. There are two kinds of players in NSE:

- Trading Members and
- Participants.

Recognized members of NSE are called trading members who trade on behalf of themselves and their clients. Participants include trading members and large players like banks who take direct settlement responsibility. Trading at NSE takes place through a fully automated screen-based trading mechanism which adopts the principle of an order-driven market. Trading members can stay at their offices and execute the trading, since they are linked through a communication network. The prices at which the buyer and seller are willing to transact will appear on the screen. When the prices match the transaction will be completed and a confirmation slip will be printed at the office of the trading member. NSE has several advantages over the traditional trading exchanges. They are as follows: NSE brings an integrated stock market trading network across the nation. Investors can trade at the same price from anywhere in the country since inter-market operations are streamlined coupled with the countrywide access to the securities.

Further the market capitalisation of different countries of the world shown in the Table 1.3 below reveals which of the country has reported growth in market capitalisation as one of the major countries capitalisation in respect of annual reports.

Out of 10 countries which are reporting market capitalisation as one of the major factor, only USA have high growth 29.70 % in %age of world market cap 2010 in comparisons to market cap in US Dollar Billions 2007 which was 17923. India has 8th position in 2010 in the growth of market capitalisation in terms of US Dollar Billions.

Table: 1.3
The Market Capitalisation of different Countries of the World

Name of the Countries with Sl. No.	Market cap (US\$ b) 2007	% of world Market-cap 2010
1 USA	17,923	29.70%
2 Japan	4,615	7.97%
3 China	3,059	6.89%
4 United Kingdom	3,722	6.72%
5 Hong Kong	2,180	4.97%
6 Canada	1,620	3.74%
7 France	2,653	3.55%
8 India	1,090	3.22%
9 Germany	1,976	2.84%
10 Brazil	-	2.84%

Source: ETIG, November 2010/ August 2007

The data given below in table 1.4 compiled by the security exchange board of India in 2011 from various secondary source reveals that growth Indian stock exchanges in particular area is declined and in the special area like stock exchanges in derivative market and currency derivative have grown up, where we can see new innovation and growth in positive sense in Indian capital market. Many stock exchanges have closed because of integration of trading on BSE, NSE, and some other exchanges because of online trading on these stock exchanges. Further in detail, time to time SEBI announced the validity period and status of permanency of different Indian stock exchanges in capital market recorded in the table no. 1.4 are as follow.

Table 1.4

DETAILED LIST OF THE INDIAN STOCK EXCHANGES		
Sr. No.	Name of the Exchange	Valid Upto
1	Ahmedabad Stock Exchange Ltd.	PERMANENT
2	Bangalore Stock Exchange Ltd.	PERMANENT
3	Bhubaneswar Stock Exchange Ltd.	June 04, 2012
4	Bombay Stock Exchange Ltd.	PERMANENT
5	Calcutta Stock Exchange Ltd.	PERMANENT
6	Cochin Stock Exchange Ltd.	November 07, 2011
7	Coimbatore Stock Exchange Ltd.	September 17, 2006
8	Delhi Stock Exchange Ltd	PERMANENT
9	Gauhati Stock Exchange Ltd	April 30, 2012
10	Hyderabad Stock Exchange Ltd	

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Due to pending litigation before the Hon'ble Madras High Court, Coimbatore Stock Exchange Ltd. (CSX) has not filed application for renewal of recognition which expired on 17.09.06. However, in terms of order dated 15.09.06 of the Hon'ble Court, the right of CSX to apply for renewal shall be subject to further orders of the court and the stock exchange shall not be entitled to oppose the renewal solely on the ground of lapse of time.

The Hyderabad Stock Exchange Ltd. (HSE) failed to dilute at least 51% of its equity share capital to public other than shareholders having trading rights on or before the stipulated date i.e. August 28, 2007. Consequently, in terms of section 5(2) of the Securities Contracts (Regulation) Act, 1956, the recognition granted to HSE stands withdrawn with effect from August 29, 2007.

11	Interconnected Stock Exchange of India Ltd.	November 17, 2011
12	Jaipur Stock Exchange Ltd.	January 08, 2012
13	Ludhiana Stock Exchange Ltd.	April 27, 2012
14	Madhya Pradesh Stock Exchange Ltd	PERMANENT
15	Madras Stock Exchange Ltd.	PERMANENT
16	Magadha Stock Exchange Ltd. ("SEBI vide order dated September 3, 2007 refused to renew the recognition granted to Magadha Stock Exchange Ltd.")	-----
17	* Mangalore Stock Exchange (As per Securities Appellate Tribunal order dated October 4, 2006, the Mangalore Stock Exchange is a de-recognized Stock Exchange under Section 4 (4) of SCRA)	-----
18	MCX Stock Exchange Ltd	September 15, 2011
19	National Stock Exchange of India Ltd.	PERMANENT
20	OTC Exchange of India	August 22, 2012
21	Pune Stock Exchange Ltd.	September 01, 2012
22	Saurashtra Kutch Stock Exchange Ltd. (SEBI vide order dated July 06, 2007 has withdrawn the recognition granted to Saurashtra Kutch Stock Exchange Limited)	-----
23	U.P. Stock Exchange Limited	June 02, 2012
24	United Stock Exchange of India Limited	March 21, 2012
25	The Vadodara Stock Exchange Ltd.	January 03, 2012

Sources: SEBI Announcement in 2011 on SEBI website.

As per SEBI announcement in 2011 on SEBI website the list of credit rating agencies is in India with name and registered office given below in the table 1.5. According to the table we have 6 major credit rating agencies in India, which are providing the trading capacity of the different business organisation with their

customers. These credit rating agencies provide grading to business organisation after studying the many factors internal and external of the business concern for benefits of general public in India as well as for Government and other financial institutions for providing loan and other facilities.

Table: 1.5

The List of Credit Rating Agencies is in India with Name and Registered Addresses.

NAME AND REGISTERED ADDRESS OF CREDIT RATING AGENCIES	
1. CRISIL Limited CRISIL House, Central Avenue, Hiranandani Business Park, Powai, Mumbai 400 076 Tel: + 91 (22) 56913001 – 09 Fax: + 91 (22) 56913010 Website: www.crisil.com	2. Fitch Ratings India Private Ltd. Apeejay House, 6th Floor, 3 Dinshaw Vachha Road, Churchgate, Mumbai 400 020 Tel: + 91 (022) 56370920-23 Fax: + 91 (022) 56370924 Website: www.fitchratings.com
3. ICRA Limited 1105, Kailash Building, 11th Floor 26, Kasturba Gandhi Marg, New Delhi 110 001 Tel: + 91 (11) 23357940 – 50 Fax: + 91 (11) 23357014 Website: www.icra.in Email: info@icraindia.com	4. Credit Analysis & Research Ltd. (CARE) 4th Floor, Godrej Coliseum Somaiya Hospital Road, Behind Everard Nagar, Off Eastern Express Highway, Sion (E), Mumbai 400 022, Tel: + 91 (22) 566 02871-73 Fax: + 91 (22) 566 02876 Website: www.careratings.com Email: care@careratings.com
5. Brickwork Ratings India Private Limited 3rd Floor, Raj Alkaa Park, 29/3 & 32/2, Kalena Agrahara, Bannerghatta Road, Bangalore – 560 076, Tel: +91 (80) 4040 9940 Fax: +91 (80) 4040 9941 Website: www.brickworkratings.in Email: info@brickworkratings.com	6. SME Rating Agency of India Ltd. (SMERA) Unit No. 102, 1st Floor, Sumer Plaza, Marol Maroshi Road, Marol, Andheri (East), Mumbai 400 059, Tel: + 91 (22) 67141144-45 Fax: + 91 (22) 67141142 Website: www.smera.in Email: info@smera.in

Sources: SEBI Announcement in 2011 on SEBI website.

CONCLUSION

The area of Indian capital market is very broad. Here I have discussed aspect related to growth pattern of Indian stock exchanges and credit rating agencies in Indian little bit other factors. The Indian stock exchanges have undergone rapid growth during post financial sectors reform in on particular line. but it is found that after 2004-05 that new types of special stock exchanges has been started in Indian capital market like stock exchanges in derivative market and in currency derivative market. Particular line trend of stock exchanges has declined and it was numbered 19 stock exchanges with 7 other stock exchanges in specific area like derivative market and currency derivative. Because of centralisation of trading deal on BSE, NSE and KSE have increased

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REFERENCES AND BIBLIOGRAPHY

1. Gupta R. (2014), 'Indian Capital market: an overview', International Journal of Emerging Research in Management & Technology, Vol-3, issue-5.
2. (2010), "Overview of Indian Capital Market-scribd, available electronic copy at <https://www.scribd.com/doc/.../ Overview of Indian Capital Market>.
3. Capital market in India, "available electronic copy at [zakirhusainpgeve.in/.../..](http://zakirhusainpgeve.in/...)

Official Report and Documents:

- 1 Reserve Bank of India Annual Report
- 2 Ministry of Finance
- 3 Security Exchange Board of India
- 4 BSE and NSE Statistics
- 5 SEBI Bulletins

Websites:

- 1 Yahoo Finance.com
- 2 Google.com
- 3 Rediff finance.com

Newspapers:

- 1 The Times of India
- 2 Economics Times
- 3 The Hindu
- 4 Hindustan Time
- 5 The Tribune
- 6 The Financial Express